

APHORISMS AS AN OBJECT OF LINGUISTIC RESEARCH

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The abstract: This paper deals with the cognitive study of the conceptual field of the English language aphorism. The methodology of the cognitive analysis of the textual concepts has been proposed and applied for the study of the means of verbalization of concept SCIENCE in English aphorisms.

Key words and phrases: language picture of the world, concept, phraseological units, science.

An aphorism is a concise, terse, laconic, or memorable expression of a general truth or principle. They are often handed down by tradition from generation to generation.

An aphorism is a saying that concisely expresses a moral principle or an observation about the world, presenting it as a general or universal truth. The Rolling Stones are responsible for penning one of the catchiest aphorisms of all time: "You can't always get what you want." Aphorisms are often (though not always) witty or humorous, and they're used everywhere, from philosophical texts and great works of literature, to pop songs and everyday conversation.

According to V.A.Maslova, the method of conceptual analysis is determined by the structural features of the concept. In particular, the core of the concept is formed by the dictionary meanings of a certain lexeme, and the periphery consists of subjective experience, pragmatic components of the lexeme and connotations [1]

The importance of aphorisms, their ancient origins and widespread use cannot be denied. But despite the fact that a large number of literary people are devoted to the genre of aphorisms, ideas about it are very vague, do not have clear outlines. There are a number of problems that remain unsolved: the word "aphorism" itself has no generally accepted concept; not established genre boundaries and specific features of aphorisms; there is no generally accepted classification of aphoristic statements, their functions in various types of texts. [2]

First of all, it is necessary to understand the etymology of the word aphoristics. Aphoristics - (from the Greek Aphorismos - definition. Short dictum. From Greek *ἀφορισμός*: aphorismos, denoting 'delimitation', 'distinction', and "definition") [3]. In the Greek language there was a word "aphorismos" - that is, a short dictum, definition... The main concept on which it relies and operates aphorism, is the concept of aphorism. The distinctive features of an aphorism are usually described by comparing it with phenomena and concepts that are close or contiguous in some way

Here it is necessary to pay special attention to one thing. It is the fact that until now A. Navoi's aphorisms have been published several times in separate collections. But most of the aphorisms included in them are taken from the poet's works such as "Khamsa", "Mahbub-ul-Qulub", "Munshaot". Of course, the selected verses or sentences fully meet the requirements of aphorisms with their content, imagery and form. But since they were not created as special aphorisms, they cannot meet the requirements of the first group of aphorisms [4].

The second group includes aphorisms as judgments and conclusions with a late and deep philosophical content, which are concise in form and come in certain philosophical researches or scientific researches. For example, Frances Bacon's 2-volume book "Aphorisms on the Interpretation of Nature and Human Rule", works entitled "On the Wisdom of the Ancients", L.Feuerbach's "Writer and Man", "Funny, Philosophical Aphorisms", F.Nissche's collection of "Wicked Wisdom" are among them.

In Uzbek linguistics and literary studies, aphorism has not been specially studied as a special object of research. In Uzbek folklore studies, A.Abdurahimov conducted scientific research on the ways and methods of giving folk aphorisms in dictionaries. But not all his views can be applied to literary aphorisms [5].

In addition, in his research proverbs, proverbs, catchphrases and phrases are not consistently distinguished from aphorisms. Only then will the reader have no doubts about the thought expressed in the aphorism, there will be no room for clarifying questions, in short, the person will fully admit to the aphoristic thought.

A.Kahhor's aphorism "Literature is stronger than an atom, but its power should not be spent on burning wood" is widely known among our people. But only a writer like A.Kahhor can say such a sharp conflicting aphorism in such a form, in such a spirit, to express things that contradict each other, but are not completely equal. Because he

was well aware of the influence of literature, he lived by this faith in his life. Therefore, he was a writer who raised the level of his belief that it is necessary not to spend the power of something more powerful than an atom on simple trifles.

Some additional key details about aphorisms:

- Aphorisms are memorable and convincing because of their pithiness. This pithiness can also be a weakness, though, since it usually means that bold assertions are being made without any elaboration or evidence to back them up.
- Many commonly used aphorisms are actually paraphrased quotations from literary, philosophical, political, and religious texts.
- Aphorisms are closely related to proverbs and adages. See below for more details on the relationships between these terms [6].

Aphorism in Everyday Speech

This list represents just a small fraction of the aphorisms people commonly use in everyday speech.

- You can lead a horse to water, but you can't make it drink.
- All is fair in love and war.
- A jack of all trades is master of none.
- Measure twice, cut once.
- An apple a day keeps the doctor away.
- Better safe than sorry.
- Better the devil you know than the devil you don't.

Aphorisms allow people to convey an idea or even a worldview using just a few words. As a result, they are used frequently in everyday speech, as well as in all types of literature. Some aphorisms are regional **colloquialisms** that originated as folk sayings, but even aphorisms that originate in literature are often quoted and repeated frequently enough that they become common in everyday speech.

It's important to remember that aphorisms do not have to express ideas that all people believe are true, or ideas that are true in every situation (if that were the case, aphorisms would be incredibly rare). Rather, an aphorism expresses an idea that *someone* (and usually the speaker) holds to be universally or generally true, though aphorisms can also be used to **satirize** (make fun of) ideas that others believe to be true.

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